

Long-term Projection of Hourly Electricity Demand with Sectoral Decomposition for Developing Economies: Bangladesh Case Study

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Abstract

Electricity is one of the cleanest forms of final energy. With the growth of economy and industrialization, many of the developing countries face increased demand of energy and electricity. In order to meet the growing demand in an economically efficient way, proper prediction of hourly load and appropriate planning is important. Bangladesh being one of the developing countries, experienced steady economic growth and increasing electricity demand over the last decade. Electricity generation has increased more than twice and share of people having access to electricity reached from 47% in 2009 to 94% in 2019. So far, the household sector is the main contributor in electricity consumption. However, as the access to electricity reaches saturation, industry and service sectors would play significant role in coming decades in terms of both electricity consumption amount and pattern. In this study, we analyze the projected electricity demand from the year 2020 to 2050 at an interval of 5 years and decompose the total demand into sectoral contribution from household, industry, service and other sectors. In addition, the hourly load demand pattern of each sector has been synthesized so that the overall changes in the daily electricity demand pattern for different seasons could be identified.

Key words: Electricity Demand, Hourly Load Curve, Long-term Projection, Developing Economies, Bangladesh,

1. Introduction

Energy is a key factor to development and growth. United Nations' (UN) Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 7¹⁾ also recognizes the importance of "ensuring access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy for all" as one of the major goals to be achieved in near future. Even though almost one billion people of the world do not have access to electricity²⁾, many efforts are being deployed globally to increase electrification rate. Many of the developing nations are facing increased demand of electricity as people's way of living changes and the traditional agriculture based society transforms into more industry and commercial service dependent ones. Bangladesh, a geographically small developing country in the south Asia, does not have a significant footprint in the global economy. However, stable growth over the last decade and rapid electrification rate with potential active workforce project that this country might require significant energy infrastructure development, especially in the electricity sector in order to continue with the development growth and changing socio-economic scenario. Advanced planning and timely implementation is thus very important to ensure the energy and electricity infrastructures in place in time. Optimal power generation mix modelling (OPGM) is one of the

ways to develop the pathway for efficient financing of electricity infrastructure for a certain geographical area. One of the basic prerequisites of OPGM is to predict future demand growth and preferably hourly load data of a future time point in order to obtain high temporal resolution. The future load curves may not have the same shape of load patterns with respect to historical data as the contribution from different consumer sectors including household, industry, service, agriculture and transport varies over time and the growth pattern also varies in differently for different sectors.

There have been several studies on short-term and long-term electrical load forecasting, a review of which reveals that regression models are widely used for long term prediction³⁾. These methods try to relate consumption of electricity directly with GDP and economic growth. However, in this analysis, we relate the overall economic growth with the sectoral growth dynamics over a long period of time and focus on the impact of individual sectoral demand growth to final energy consumption, particularly in the electricity sector. Moreover, sectoral contribution from different consumer sectors and their individual load patterns are also taken into consideration to project the future long-term overall load patterns. Such analysis for developing countries which go through a shift in economic activities during the analysis period is unique and first of a kind for Bangladesh.

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2. Methodology

Different energy and electricity demand models exist including MEDEE/MAED, LEAP, POLES, WEM, which focus on different aspects of the energy system from different perspectives ⁴⁾. The MAED model is rather specialized to model energy and electricity demand for developing economies as it considers the dynamics of consumer sectors and energy technologies in detail which was previously applied for analyzing the future final energy demand for Bangladesh up to the year 2050 ⁵⁾. The output of MAED_D model from the previous analysis is used as the basic input for MAED_EI model for this analysis to project the future load-curves.

In this analysis, the annual electricity demand of a consumer sector is converted into the electric power requested by the same sector at a given hour of a certain day and week of the corresponding year by taking into account the following factors:

- (i) The trend of the average growth rate of the demand over the year;
- (ii) The variation of electricity consumption due to the seasonal impact (which could be expressed in terms of semesters, quarters, months, weeks);
- (iii) The impact of the type of day considered in the electricity consumption (whether a working day, a weekend or holiday etc.);
- (iv) The variation of energy consumption due to the period of the day considered (whether in the morning, lunchtime, evening etc.).

Each of these factors is represented by a certain coefficient that in a sense "modulates" the electric power requested by the sector (thus, they are called load-modulating coefficients).

In this model, the year is divided into six seasons and a special holiday period, which may have different electricity consumption pattern from these six seasons. Similarly, the starting and the ending dates of the special holiday period (e.g. 'Ramadan' for Muslim majority countries like Bangladesh) are also defined. The sequence of the weekdays (for example, from Sunday to Thursday for Bangladesh) and the typical days for hourly load variation (for example, working day, Friday and Saturday as weekend for Bangladesh) are also specified.

Several coefficients are calculated from the base year which modulate the future electricity demand pattern at different time points which are described below:

2.1 Electricity yearly demand growth coefficient $T_c(w)$:

In order to consider a standard day, the first correction to be made corresponds to the general trend of the growth of electricity consumption during the year. This is represented by a 'deflator' which is calculated on a weekly basis (with a total of 53 values in the year), so that the deflator of the gross electricity consumption (i.e. the growth trend coefficient) of a sector c for week w is:

$$T_c(w) = \left[1 + \frac{GROWTH_c}{100} \right]^{\left(\frac{w-26}{52} \right)} \quad (1)$$

where, $GROWTH_c$ is the average annual growth rate of electricity demand of the current sector between the previous and the current year which is either specified (for the first year) or calculated by the program from the information read from the MAED_D ⁶⁾.

2.2 Seasonal coefficients $K_c(w)$:

In order to take into account the seasonal impact on electricity consumption of a sector, the 'seasonal deflator' is used. For the time period (either a semester, a quarter, a month, a week etc.), K_c represents the average weight of this period in the total electricity consumption for the year.

Fig. 1 Seasonal coefficients for the base-year (2016)

In this model, the week has been selected as the elementary time unit for representing these seasonal variations and, therefore, 53 $K_c(w)$ coefficients must be given as input data for each reference year of study period, keeping in mind that at least one of the first and last week will be not an entire week. The seasonal coefficients for the base year as shown in Fig. 1 identifies the seasonal variations including holiday seasons with lower coefficients and high demand hot and humid seasons with higher coefficients.

2.3 Daily ponderation coefficients: $P_c(w, d)$:

This type of coefficient reflects fluctuations of electricity consumption due to the type of day being considered, i.e. a working day, weekends and holidays, etc. Since the general goal

of the model is to compare the electricity consumption of every time unit to the consumption in the equivalent working day, the relative weight of a working day is chosen to be equal to 1, and the other types of day are weighted in comparison to their relative consumption relative to that of the working day, e.g. a Saturday could be assumed at 0.8 of a working day, a Friday at 0.7, etc. Daily ponderation coefficients are calculated from the base year sectoral energy data E_{0c} to identify the impacts of weekends and holidays and their deviation from regular weekdays.

$$P_c(w, d) = \frac{E_{0c}(7w+d)}{\frac{1}{53} \sum_{w'=0}^{52} E_{0c}(7w'+d)} \quad (2)$$

The same daily coefficients could be used for future analysis years with minor revision due to shifting of religious holidays linked with the lunar calendar. In general, these coefficients fluctuate over the year according to the time period considered (week, in this case) so that they are more properly represented as $P_c(w, d)$, $w = 0$ to 52 and $d = 0$ to 6.

2.4 Hourly coefficients: $LCS_s(h, i)$:

The objective of the hourly coefficient is to weigh the energy consumption over the 24 hours of the day. Each hour, h of a day would be given a coefficient according to the level of consumption in the hour in such a way so that the sum of the coefficients over the day is equal to 24.

In general, these coefficients are dependent on the time period of the year and the typical days for hourly load variation being considered. Concerning the variation according to the time period of the year, a differentiation can be made in the program between the consumption in each of the six seasons as well as for the special holiday period. Several types of clients or consumers with varying daily load characteristics can also be distinguished for the sector being considered.

Each client type c (industry, service, household, and agriculture-transport) has a weight in each day type i , where i could be either weekdays (wd) or weekend-holidays (wh) and for each season s equal to $LCONT_{s,c,i}$ as well as hourly variation of electricity demand $LCOEF_{s,c,i}(h)$ which are given as input. Consequently, from these data the program calculates the seasonal aggregated hourly coefficients $LCS_{s,i}$ for each hour h :

$$LCS_{s,i}(h) = \sum_{c=1}^4 LCONT_{s,c,i} \cdot LCOEF_{s,c,i}(h) \quad (3)$$

The sum of hourly coefficient factors for the whole day of a particular season and day-type must equal to 24.

2.5 Number of equivalent working days in a year

Having identified all above-mentioned coefficients, the total number N_c of equivalent working days for a particular year and sector c is:

$$N_c = \sum_{w=1}^{53} \sum_{d=1}^7 P_c(w, d) \cdot K_c(w) \cdot T_c(w) \quad (4)$$

Thus, the energy consumption of the sector in the equivalent average working day:

$$EWDS_c = \frac{ENERGY_c}{N_c} \quad (5)$$

where, $ENERGY_c$ is the annual electricity consumption of the current sector c in the current model year estimated with MAED_D model.

2.6 Determination of the average hourly demand of the sector

The total electricity consumption of the current sector c for the calendar day m ($=7w+d$) of current year is given by:

$$E_c(m) = EWDS_c \cdot K_c(w) \cdot T_c(w) \cdot P_c(w, d) \quad (6)$$

The dynamic relation between calendar day m of a year and day-type i_m is manually defined in the model and electric power demand PV of the sector c in hour h of the day m is calculated as:

$$PV_{s,c}(h, m) = \frac{E_c(m) \cdot LCS_s(h, i_m)}{24} \quad (7)$$

where, $m=0$ to 364.

Finally, the total annual electricity demand of the sector is:

$$ESUM_c = \sum_m E_c(m) \quad (8)$$

The coefficients described above are calculated and the methodology is applied to each of the four sectors considered in the program, i.e. household, industry, service and agriculture-transport sectors. Once all sectoral total annual demand and hourly loads have been determined, the program calculates the total annual demand of the power generating system, ET and the growth rate $GROWAV$ of this demand for the current year as:

$$ET = \sum_{c=1}^4 ESUM_c \quad (9)$$

$$GROWAV = \sum_{c=1}^4 ESUM_c \cdot \frac{GROWTH_c}{ET} \quad (10)$$

The total electric load imposed to the generating system in hour h is obtained by adding the load of all sectors for that hour h , i.e.:

$$PT_s(h, m) = \sum_{c=1}^4 PV_{s,c}(h, m) \quad (11)$$

3. Input Data

3.1 Base data for historical electricity demand

Hourly load data for the year 2016 is considered as the base for different coefficient calculation as described in section 2. Bangladesh is a land of six seasons due to its sub-tropical monsoon climate. Each season comprises two months, but some seasons flow into other seasons, while others are short. The six seasons are: summer (from mid-April to mid-June), rainy season (from mid-June to mid-August), autumn (mid-August to mid-October), late autumn (from mid-October to mid-December), winter (from mid-December to mid-February) and spring (from mid-February to mid-April). Seasonal variation in the load data for weekdays (*wd*) and weekend-holidays (*wh*) for the base year is presented in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 Load-curves in different seasons for the base year 2016

3.2 Population projection

The population growth projection was considered as per the median projection as proposed by UN ⁷⁾ and shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3 Year-wise population projection of Bangladesh

3.3 Economic growth and transition for scenario analysis

Three different socio-economic scenarios in terms of real GDP growth rate are considered in this analysis and named as Business As Usual (BAU), Low Economic Growth (LEG) and High Economic Growth (HEG). These scenarios consider the currently increasing GDP growth rate reaches 8% by the year 2020 and from that point linearly decrease up to 4%, 5% and 6% for the LEG, BAU and HEG scenarios respectively as in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4 GDP Projections for different socio-economic scenarios

3.4 Economic transition

Even though agriculture used to play a significant role in the economy of Bangladesh, significant growth has been observed in the industry sector. The current high growth in the industry sector is mainly caused by large scale infrastructure development projects including the Padma Multipurpose Bridge, the Rooppur Nuclear Power Plant, the Dhaka Mass Rapid Transit (metro-rail), the Payra and Sonadia sea ports, the Maheshkhali floating Liquid Natural Gas terminal project, and several large power projects which require huge steel and cement production ⁸⁾. It is expected to continue as consumption from all other commercial, public and household sectors grow with the country's economic development in the long run. Per-capita steel consumption almost doubled in the last decade and it is expected to grow in coming years. The historical growth trend in the economic sectors is shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5 Historical growth in major economic sectors ⁹⁾

The ongoing and planned mega projects confirm that industry sector will continue to grow. The model input for projected sectoral GDP contribution as shown in Fig. 6 is developed based on criteria that contribution from industry sector would continue to rise steadily until 2050.

Fig. 6 Projected sectoral GDP contribution in the economy

3.5 Social dynamics

As the economy grows, people’s purchasing power increases and residential consumption for air-conditioning and use of modern electrical appliances also increase significantly. The other factors including population distribution in the country (e.g. urban and rural), changes in life style, population mobility growth, passenger and freight transportation and market penetration of competing energy forms which also influence the energy and electricity demand over time, were considered for analyzing different scenarios.

3.6 Sectoral energy and electricity demand

The future electricity demand for combined industry, household, service and agriculture-transport sectors for different analysis years (from 2020 to 2050 at 5 years interval) were obtained from the BAU, LEG and HEG cases of MAED_D analysis previously performed⁵⁾ and as presented in Fig 7.

Fig. 7 Electricity demand from 2020 to 2050 at different economic growth scenarios

Each of these scenarios could be further decomposed into economic sub-sectors, which is shown for the BAU case in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8 Sectoral decomposition of electricity demand BAU case

3.7 Coefficients for detail electricity demand modelling

The seasonal coefficients $K_c(w)$, daily ponderation coefficients $P_c(w, d)$ and hourly coefficients $LCS_s(h, i)$ were calculated using the base year 2016 load data as shown in Fig. 1 and 2. In order to simplify the calculation complexities, same coefficient sets were used for future projection years as well. Sectoral load curves for the industry, household, service, and agriculture-transport sectors were assumed based on traditional load-pattern of similar developing nations as such detail data with hourly resolution was not available for Bangladesh. For the future load-curve patterns of individual sectors, a modulating pattern was used considering currently developed and industrialized country’s load patterns.

4. Results analysis

The primary objective of the analysis to obtain the hourly load-curves for each individual economic sector and the overall electricity sector so that proper planning and timely execution could be performed for optimal power generation mix formulation, appropriate financing to ensure stable electricity production and thus contribute to the national development. Results were calculated at 5 years interval starting from 2020 and ending at 2050. The resulting load-curves show a changing pattern due to

Fig. 9 Representative load curve of a summer week in 2050 with sectoral contribution

the consequence of shifting from traditional house-hold dominated consumption to industry and service sectors dominated consumption. Agriculture and transport sectors also play some role as irrigation using electric pump and metro-transportation become popular. A representative load-curve of a week (Sunday to Saturday) in the summer of 2050 is presented in Fig. 9 with sectoral decomposition so that the variations could be observed.

The chronological shift in the loading patterns could be observed from Fig. 10 through the normalized load curves of different years.

Fig. 10 Normalized daily load-curves from 2020 to 2050

It is quite obvious that current loading pattern has a relatively large peak in the evening due to lighting requirement at the household. With the growth of economy and transferring to the industry and commercial service based society, the ratio of peak to average load would decrease. Moreover, there might be additional peak in the day-time due to high consumption in the office and industries. These kinds of results also suggest to make necessary adaptations in the unit commitment policy and spinning reserve margin for maximum efficiency with necessary security. The seasonal and weekly (Sunday to Saturday) variation in a particular year, in this case for 2050 could be observed from Fig. 11. It is to be noted that Friday and Saturday are the weekends in the country when the peak load is found to be reduced from ~5% to 10% with respect to weekdays, depending on the season. Moreover, summer is not always the season when maximum load is expected. Due to the tropical weather, average temperature in the country reaches around 30°C in mid-spring (March) and it remains around the same or higher temperature until the end of autumn (October). Historical data shows that annual peak demand of electricity normally occurs in June as cooling requirements become highest due to hot and humid weather. The analysis results reflect the effect of seasonal coefficients as shown in Fig. 1 and base year load data of 2016, as presented in Fig. 2.

Fig. 11 Seasonal and weekly load variation in the load in 2050

The Bangladesh Government has already adopted a Power System Master Plan (PSMP) 2016 with projected demand up to the year 2041. The maximum demand obtained from this analysis for different scenarios is compared in Table 1 with the government projection plan for future electricity generation capacity¹⁰⁾ to justify the reliability of similar studies. The government projected the required installed generation capacity considering transmission and distribution losses and spinning reserves for future years in PSMP 2016. However, the Government projections are made by donor agencies with highly ambitious considerations focusing on building of new generation capacities rather than developing the transmission-distribution networks and improving energy efficiency. Recent studies show that average capacity utilization of the existing power plants was only 43% during the financial year 2018-19 which might deteriorate in coming days due to the global pandemic of Covid-19 and overcapacity of the existing plan¹¹⁾.

Table 1 Maximum Load projection and Planned Installed Capacity

Year	Maximum Load at Different Scenarios (GW)			Planned Installed Capacity (GW)
	LEG	BAU	HEG	
2020	10.56	10.56	10.56	13.30
2025	13.62	13.99	13.99	19.90
2030	19.08	20.42	20.42	27.40
2035	26.22	29.47	29.47	37.30
2040	35.86	41.95	42.74	48.50
2045	49.03	59.05	62.55	-
2050	67.71	82.93	93.34	-

It is observed that even for the high economic growth scenario, the projected demand is relatively lower than the government plan for installed capacity. The reasons may be the consideration of transmission and distribution losses, spinning reserve capacities and captive generations in the PSMP as it focuses on the generation expansion plan.

5. Conclusion

It is to be noted that the MAED model used in this analysis is not just a forecasting model, rather it is a simulation model designed for evaluating the energy and electricity demand of a country or world region in the medium and long term. The main objective in this research is to observe the impacts of different socio-economic and sectoral composition changes over time on the electricity demand and the load patterns which have been presented in the results analysis section. Different socio-economic scenarios and their outcomes play a significant role for efficient economic policy planning in the electricity sector of developing countries like Bangladesh. And, this study results are believed to contribute further to policy planners for efficient electricity sector development rather than simple load forecasting.

The current analysis on the hourly load-curve projection for long-term planning and optimization of power system investments provides some useful insights including change in loading pattern due to contribution from different economic sectors and shift of economy from domestic agriculture domination to industry and commercial service based economy. This analysis could also be useful for generation, transmission and distribution planning as it projects the end-user demands directly. These results could be further analyzed to obtain the optimal power generation mix for the sustainable development of the economy and energy sector at the same time. Developing countries often face a continuous growth of demand with changing patterns from different economic sectors which could be analyzed and further projected for future power system planning using the methodology applied in this paper.

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